

D6.6 Updated Communication, Dissemination and Standardisation Plan

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Control sheet

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1. Introduction

1.1. Althena concept and approach

Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions have emerged thanks to novel Artificial Intelligence (AI) which can be trained with huge amounts of data to produce driving functions with better-than-human performance under certain conditions. The race on AI keeps on building HW/SW frameworks to manage and process even larger real and synthetic datasets to train increasingly accurate AI models.

However, AI remains largely unexplored with respect to explainability (interpretability of model functioning), privacy preservation (exposure of sensitive data), ethics (bias and wanted/unwanted behaviour), and accountability (responsibilities of AI outputs). These features will establish the basis of trustworthy AI, as a novel paradigm to fully understand and trust AI in operation, while using it at its full capabilities for the benefit of society.

Althena will contribute to build Explainable AI (XAI) in CCAM development and testing frameworks, researching three main AI pillars: data (real/synthetic data management), models (data fusion, hybrid AI approaches), and testing (physical/virtual XiL set-ups with scalable MLOps).

A human-centric methodology will be created to derive trustworthy AI dimensions from user identified group needs in CCAM applications. Althena will innovate proposing a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) on XAI, and an analysis to explore trade-offs between these dimensions.

Demonstrators will show the Althena methodology in four critical use cases: perception (what does the AI perceive, and why), situational awareness (what is the AI understanding about the current driving environment, including the driver state), decision (why a certain decision is taken), and traffic management (how transport-level applications interoperate with AI-enabled systems operating at vehicle-level).

Created data and tools will be made available via European data sharing initiatives (OpenData and OpenTools) to foster research on trustworthy AI for CCAM.

1.2. Althena consortium

The Althena consortium consists of 17 partners from 6 different EU countries, and 1 associated partner from Switzerland, who gather all the necessary background and expertise to achieve the objectives of the project. Furthermore, as a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), a balance mix of partners has been selected for provisioning the research, expertise and technology required to meet the project objectives:

- research partners (VICOM, IKA, TUE, VIF, TNO, BUW),
- technology providers (TTTA, IFAG, SIE-NL, SIE-BE),
- industry (CAF, MAPTM, IDI, RC, VALEO),
- social science (TUE) and
- stakeholder associations (IRU, FIA).

To ensure the value of the project results are maximised, the symbiosis of research, technology and business will enable Althena to demonstrate direct relevance to European society and industry.

Figure 1 Distribution of Althena partners

1.3. Purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable (*D6.6 Updated Communication, Dissemination and Standardisation Plan*) is intended to present an updated version of the *D6.1 Initial Communication, Dissemination, and Standardisation Plan*, which was developed and submitted in M6 (April 2023). All planned actions in this deliverable are part of the Althena tasks: T6.1, T6.2 and T6.3. Reporting of implementation of T6.2 and T6.3 will be provided in M36 (*D6.5 Report on dissemination and standardisation activities*).

The main objective of the Althena communication, dissemination, and standardisation plan is:

- To develop key, targeted messages to different technical, scientific, industry and policy audiences.

- To define channels, dissemination opportunities, such events and scientific publications and networking activities to communicate the project and disseminate widely project results, outcomes, and achievements whenever available.

This deliverable also provides further updates and work plan for all activities in WP6 related to communication, dissemination, and standardisation. However, the focus of this deliverable as well as initial plan (M9) is to set the foundations for the three tasks:

- Task 6.1 Communication strategy.
- Task 6.2 Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation.
- Task 6.3 End user dissemination.

Task 6.1 *Communication strategy [M1-M5]* which coordinates the work in WP6 – *IMPACT: Exploitation, Dissemination and Standardisation [M1-M36]* and monitors the progress in accordance with the Althena project timeline. Additionally, T6.1 will continuously liaise with other WPs to ensure alignment of the projects output to be disseminated.

Task 6.2 *Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation [M3-M36]* will connect the Althena project's results and achievements with relevant scientific and industrial fora as well as events to disseminate the tools and knowledge generated in the project to expert audiences.

Task 6.3 *End user dissemination [M13-M36]* will be focused on preparation and implementation of an information campaign which aims to educate users about the use cases developed in the project and to promote advantages of XAI in CCAM can bring to the users.

1.4. Structure of this deliverable

This report firstly presents the consortium, work plan in WP6 and corresponding tasks, and interactions between WP6 and remaining WPs. Secondly it describes communication, dissemination and standardisation activities, channels, tools, and measures that will be used throughout the lifetime of the project.

The following chapters of this deliverable (*D6.6 Updated Communication, Dissemination and Standardisation Plan*) have been added, updated, or detailed compared to the deliverable D6.1 *Initial Communication, Dissemination, and Standardisation Plan (submitted in M9)*:

- Task 6.3 End user dissemination
- Key messages
- Target audience, channels, and messages
- Scientific and industrial dissemination, and standardisation plans
- Standardisation plans
- Yearly practitioner's workshops
- Dissemination opportunities
- Website
- Newsletters
- Information campaign (user awareness campaign)

- EU disclaimer and emblem, and SERI disclaimer
- Clustering with other projects, networking, and international initiatives
- Collaboration opportunities

Other chapters of this deliverable (D6.6) have been retained as presented in deliverable D6.1 and/or minor changes, corrections or clarifications have been made.

2. Work Package 6 - work plan and responsibilities

Task No	Task Title	Task Leader	Task Duration
6.1	Communication strategy	FIA	M1-M5[36] ¹
6.2	Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation	VALEO	M6-M36
6.3	End user dissemination	FIA	M13-M36
6.4	OpenData plan and OpenTool plan and sharing	VICOM	M17-M36
6.5	Lessons learned and policy recommendations	RC	M22-M36
6.6	Exploitation & commercialisation plan	IRU	M18-M36

Table 1 List of Tasks in Work Package 6

The focus on WP6 is to create an impact in terms of communication, dissemination, and exploitation, including standardisation. The Althena project will be communicated, the achievements will be disseminated, and the results will be exploited according to the communication, dissemination and exploitation including standardisation plan which form the core of the initial and updated plans (M9, M18).

2.1. Task 6.1 Communication strategy

This task coordinates the work in WP6 and monitors the progress in accordance with the project timeline. In addition, T6.1 will continuously liaise with the other WPs to ensure alignment of the project output with the project dissemination. A communication and dissemination strategy will be developed, identifying the knowledge to be disseminated, the target audiences to be addressed and the channels used to maximise the reach of the knowledge generated in the project. The relevant scientific and industrial fora to be addressed will be defined and a timeline for the exchange with those fora will be set. The project identity will be defined by providing tools and guidelines for the project dissemination.

¹ Task 6.1 *Communication strategy* coordinates the work in WP6 and monitors WP6 related activities in all WPs. It was therefore agreed to extend the timetable for T6.1 as M1-M36.

2.2. Task 6.2 Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation

This task will connect with the relevant scientific and industrial fora and events to disseminate the tools and knowledge generated in the project to an expert audience. The work will start with the identification of requirements and barriers for industry deployment of the developed solutions, to set the priorities for the content output. With regards to the exchange with the scientific community, the T6.2 aims to make the project output accessible via the publication of scientific papers and presentations at relevant conferences. In addition, a series of yearly practitioners' workshops will be organised to allow an in-depth exchange on the Althena developments, tools, and methods.

2.3. Task 6.3 End user dissemination

The core of T6.3 will be an information campaign which aims to educate users about the use cases developed in the project and promote the advantages XAI in CCAM can bring to the users. To provide relevant information, the content of the campaign will be aligned with the user groups and user needs defined in *Task 1.4 Identification of user group needs and definition of use cases*, as well as with Use Cases work and development in *WP5 DEPLOY & TEST: AI-based CCAM Deployment – integration on operation and end user validation*.

The campaign will use a two-pronged approach: the task will join public events to disseminate the developed information via printed materials, and presentations allowing users to gather first-hand insights into AI processes in a CCAM vehicle. In addition, an online campaign will reach users via social media. The campaign will be implemented on Althena website and social media channels (LinkedIn and X), and all Althena consortium partners will be requested to support the campaign's activity.

2.4. WP6 – staff effort per partner

All 17 Althena consortium partners have been allocated with resources for WP6 activities and, in addition to those leading and contributing to specific tasks in WP6, will support the communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities throughout the Althena implementation schedule.

Participant	WP6 effort (Person-Month)
1 - VICOM	7.00
2 - IKA	2.30
3 - TUE	2.00
4 - VIF	2.00
5 - CAF	2.00
6 - TTTA	1.00
7 - SIE-NL	4.00

8 - SIE-BE	1.00
9 - IDI	4.00
10 - RC	11.00
11 - TNO	2.20
12 - MAPTM	1.00
13 - BUW	3.00
14 - IFAG	3.50
15 - VALEO	4.50
16 - FIA	19.60
17 - IRU	9.00

Table 2 Staff effort per participant in WP6

2.5. Interactions between WP6 and other WPs in Althena project

WP6 ensures that all Work Packages in Althena project are aligned when it comes to creating the impact of communication, dissemination, and exploitation, including standardisation activities.

Figure 2 Inter-relation between WPs

2.6. Intended audience of this deliverable

The communication, and dissemination plan has a particular purpose:

- to support the overall strategy to maximise the impact of the Althena project,
- to increase the visibility of the project, and
- to ensure that the results and outputs reach a wide audience of relevant to the project stakeholders, also beyond the lifetime of the project itself.

Both the deliverables initial plan [M9] and updated plan [M18] are public reports, and both will be made available for the public on the Althena website.

This document for Althena consortium partners provides guidelines for the use of the available communications and dissemination tools and inform the consortium about procedures to be followed. For any other audience (externals to the consortium), it provides an overview of the Althena project objectives and purposes when it comes to communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities.

3. Work Package 6 - milestones and deliverables

3.1. Tasks 6.1-6.3 related deliverables

There are three deliverables which address Tasks 6.1-6.3 and are closely related to Althena communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities.

Deliverable	Type	Due date	Dissemination level	Lead beneficiary
D6.1 Initial communication, dissemination, and standardisation plan	R - Document, report	M6	PU - Public	16-FIA
D6.5 Report on dissemination and standardisation activities	R - Document, report	M36	PU - Public	16-FIA
D6.6 Updated communication, disseminations, and standardisation plan	R - Document, report	M18	PU - Public	16-FIA

Table 3 Tasks 6.1-6.3 related deliverables

3.2. Tasks 6.1-6.3 related milestones

There are four milestones related to tasks 6.1-6.3. FIA, the WP6 leader, will monitor the progress and coordinate with WP6 partners to achieve the milestones in a timely manner. In case of delays or challenges, a solution will be sought, including support from the Althena coordination team.

Milestone No	Milestone name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
6	Practitioner's workshop (year 1)	WP6	16-FIA	Event with stakeholders and experts	M12
10	Practitioner's workshop (year 2)	WP6	16-FIA	Event with stakeholders and experts	M24

15	Exploitation and standardisation plan agreed	WP6	16-FIA	To be reported in D6.1	M36
16	Practitioner's workshop (year 3)	WP6	16-FIA	Event with stakeholders and experts	M36

Table 4 Tasks 6.1-6.3 related milestones

4. Communication and dissemination plan

4.1. Objectives

The Althena communication and dissemination plan will set out a strategy to maximise the impact of the project, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that the project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders.

The Althena consortium partners represent large groups of relevant organisations, and special focus of the project will be put on connecting with networks and communication channels that all Althena partners already have, through their affiliations and relations also via digital channels (newsletters, social media channels etc.). To create impact in terms of communication, dissemination, and exploitation, including standardisation, Althena's plan will:

- Create visibility for the project output and exchange with stakeholders' community to maximise the project's impact.
- Educate users about AI applications in CCAM through an online information campaign.
- Map existing XAI standards and identify gaps in standardisation needs.
- Develop guidelines and tools to encourage privacy-preserving AI development and testing processes.
- Give policy recommendations for exploitation of XAI in CCAM based on collected lessons learned.
- Conduct an analysis of business models employing XAI in CCAM.
- Contribute to common information, dissemination activities, and synergies between HE/H2020 supported actions.

4.1.1. Purpose

The main purpose of the plan is to improve current AI development introducing trustworthiness concept from the beginning in all the dimensions of AI system implementation: design, development, deployment, and operational phases. And to raise awareness of the importance of creation of explainable AI solutions to speed up the development and deployment process of AI solutions in the field.

4.2. Key messages

Key messages will be extracted from all recommendations and guidelines developed in the project (*Task 6.5 Lessons learned and policy recommendations [M22-M36]*) ensuring brief and impactful considerations can be communicated, which will result in creating interest for the detailed Althena results to be disseminated among relevant stakeholders. An analysis of lessons learned

will provide the basis for developing policy recommendations for AI's solutions' exploitation in CCAM with focus on practical guidance for authorities and stakeholders on planning and implementing AI solutions. Consequently, the recommendations will be translated into key messages for users and disseminated via Althena channels, with support of consortium partners to reach wide range of relevant networks and stakeholders.

Additionally, AI and CCAM related relevant key messages will be extracted from existing resources and complemented with visual materials that will be created specifically for the Althena project.

Specifically, an information campaign, as a core of *T6.3 End user dissemination*, will be implemented. The campaign's main aim is to educate users about the Althena use cases developed in WP1 and WP5, and to promote the advantages XAI in CCAM can bring to users.

The key messages will be prepared in collaboration with *T1.4 Identification of user group needs and definition of use cases* and *WP5 DEPLOY & TEST: AI-based CCAM Deployment – integration on operation and end user validation* both providing user groups and user needs identifications, specific needs, challenges, and tools originating from the targeted use cases. To ensure wide reach of the Althena campaign, the project presence will be made via consortium partners at public events to disseminate developed information and outcomes (presentations, panel discussions, dedicated sessions organised, technical and scientific papers, and posters). The campaign, built around key messages, will allow users to gather first-hands insights into AI processes in a CCAM vehicle. The Althena campaign about the 4 Use Cases developed in the project with project physical presence at conferences, workshops, meetings, events etc. will be complemented by online campaign via project's social media channels as well as channels of Althena consortium partners.

4.3. Implementation phases

The communication, dissemination, and exploitation (including standardisation) plan will be structured into three main phases aligned with the Althena timetable:

- Awareness building phase.
- Participation phase.
- Action phase.

Figure 3 Althena Implementation phases

4.4. Target audience, channels, and messages

The initial analysis proposed by consortium partners has identified the following Althena target groups, pathways and channels, and key messages and means to be used. Further analysis will be carried out and the consortium partners will be able to propose new target groups and messages if these are relevant to the Althena project.

Target group	Pathways and channels	Key messages and means
Technical experts, and scientific community	Events, scientific congresses, journal papers, dedicated workshops	XAI can be applied to CCAM. Althena novel XAI and data management methods obtain satisfactory performance results.
CCAM value chain	Events, meetings, dedicated workshops, webinars, congresses, website, social media	Althena's harmonised XAI methodology addresses all driving subsystems (perception, prediction, and decision) and improves trustworthiness.
Public	Social media, popular magazines	Reliability of AI based solutions thanks to the trustworthiness and explainable approach proposed by Althena -raise public acceptance

Standardisation	Dedicated workshops and meetings, interoperability, and compliance events	Demonstration of real-world usage and recommendations for CCAM XAI adoption. Integration of ongoing and new standards in project activities with focus on data management
Authorities / certification bodies	Events, specialised workshops with each of the main actors in the adoption of Althena methodology: authorities, certification, standardisation bodies. Dedicated workshops and user centred activities will be organised to provide insight in the X-AI approach and adoption of methodologies for CCAM	Testing and Validation approaches: Validation procedures can be improved adopting Althena’s approach. Lessons learnt about the application of XAI in CCAM: limitations and ethical considerations. Standardisation and certification: Althena methodology development and adoption – specific use case analysis and demos Application cases and use cases for local public authorities for considering ethics and explainability requirements for current and future CCAM solution and services to be deployed
End users	Partners’ networks: FIA (Mobility Clubs, Transport & Mobility; Legal & Consumer Affairs and Technical Working Groups) and IRU (IRU’s committee for passenger and goods transport, technical committee)	Demonstrated solutions, application of AI solutions in road transport.

Table 5 Althena Target audiences

5. Scientific and industrial dissemination, and standardisation plans

5.1. Standardisation plans

In the dynamic landscape of Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) applications, ensuring the safety and trustworthiness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems is paramount. Standardisation activities, led by entities like the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), play a

crucial role in establishing a structured and universally accepted framework for developing, deploying, and assessing AI technologies within the CCAM ecosystem.

Addressing the complexities arising from the non-deterministic nature of AI, standardisation efforts encounter unique challenges. Traditionally, evaluating systems involves testing their behaviour in specific scenarios; however, the inherent unpredictability of AI outputs poses difficulties in applying conventional evaluation methods. Despite these challenges, establishing safety standards for AI in CCAM applications is essential to mitigate risks, manage uncertainties, and foster cross-industry collaboration.

Scientific and industrial dissemination, and standardisation activities serve as a common ground for defining safety requirements, risk assessment methodologies, and best practices specific to the unique challenges posed by AI in CCAM. Adhering to recognised standards becomes crucial for stakeholders, enabling them to enhance user trust, facilitate regulatory compliance, and promote continuous improvement in developing and deploying AI technologies.

Furthermore, relevant project results will be incorporated into standardisation efforts to increase the impact of what has been achieved in the Althena project. The identification of concrete standardisation bodies as well as project results worthy of standardisation will be done during the project's implementation.

In the realm of AI standardisation and certification, multiple frameworks and initiatives have been established to ensure the reliability, safety, and ethical considerations of automated systems. The ISO/IEC 5338:2023 defines comprehensive AI system life cycle processes, offering a structured approach encompassing the definition, control, management, execution, and improvement of AI systems throughout their life cycle stages. When dealing with traditional software or systems within AI elements, ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207 and ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 life cycle processes can be employed.

A significant standard in the domain of AI safety is the ISO/PAS 21448 SOTIF, specifically addressing risks associated with the intended functionality of automated driving systems. As a complementary standard to ISO26262, SOTIF concentrates on ensuring the safety of automated driving systems, even in unforeseen situations, without system failures. This involves preventing, controlling, and mitigating safety hazards related to the intended function rather than malfunctions.

The IEEE CertifAIEd™ certification program focuses on assessing the ethics of Autonomous Intelligent Systems (AIS). While emphasizing ethical values such as transparency, accountability, algorithmic bias, and privacy, the program provides a label for organisations to demonstrate their commitment to building trust in their systems.

In August 2022, the European Commission adopted Regulation 2022/1426, establishing rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 concerning the type-approval of the automated driving system (ADS) in fully automated vehicles. Siemens Industry Software Netherlands B.V., RDW (the Netherlands Vehicle Authority), and JRC (European Commission's Joint Research Center) have collaborated to interpret and apply this new regulation, with a focus on the simulation credibility assessment framework.

To disseminate these activities and provide guidance, Siemens has created a website: [Multi-pillar approach for safety validation of automated vehicles - Simcenter \(siemens.com\)](https://www.siemens.com/simcenter/multi-pillar-approach-for-safety-validation-of-automated-vehicles)

Additionally, a simulation handbook is set to be released by the end of 2024 (jointly by RDW, JRC, and Siemens), offering guidance for Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and type approval authorities on the application of virtual testing during the certification of automated driving systems (ADS) in fully automated vehicles. This multi-pillar approach underscores the commitment to safety validation in the evolving landscape of automated vehicle technologies.

Looking ahead, ongoing efforts in standardisation are essential to address the gaps not covered by existing standards. The challenges faced by practitioners and standardisation bodies in the CCAM industry have been identified, and further regulations and standardisations are needed to address these issues comprehensively. Beringhoff et al². identified 31 challenges that need to be addressed.

A summary of the challenges can be found in the following table:

Scenario-based testing (SBT)	Simulation-based testing	Test automation	Test execution
Terminology. not even the word scenario has a standard meaning	Purely simulation-based sign-off not yet possible: simulation still not the same as reality	Lack of test automation	Omission of the test driver
Consistent scenario description. OpenSCENARIO is working on this	Determination of trustworthiness of simulation results	Interaction between test automation, object, and infrastructure	Realisation of test conditions
Complexity of scenarios	Certification of simulation tools	Test implementation effort	Coordination of the surrounding traffic
Multifunctional scenario description. they are needed for testing but also developing and each task has different requirements	Identification of simulation-suitable tests		
Coupling scenarios and test cases	Unknown effects: effects that occur and were not added to simulation		
Consistent scenario interpretation	Choice of simulation method		

² Beringhoff, F., Greenyer, J., Roesener, C., & Tichy, M. (2022, June). Thirty-one challenges in testing automated vehicles: Interviews with experts from industry and research. In *2022 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)* (pp. 360-366). IEEE.

Scenario elicitation. What scenarios are relevant? Difficulty to identify them before release	Lack of simulation models
Scenario space and use of corner cases	Validation of simulation models
Scenario generation	Driver models
SBT on proving grounds: control of traffic, safety concerns...	Sensor simulation
Scenario concatenation	Weather effects
Test end criteria: formalise when enough has been tested	Integration of the test object in the simulation environment
Comparison to distance metrics	

Table 6 Summary of standardisation challenges

5.2. Yearly practitioners' workshops

The Althena project aims at organising workshops that could be held in conjunction with relevant conferences, congresses, or other relevant events. The topic of the workshop could be related to "Trustworthy and Explainable AI". Project partners will aim for conferences that have a high reputation and belong to the computer vision and machine learning domain, e.g., the IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium. For this purpose, a successful application process must be passed, and the best workshop concept must prevail from many applicants.

Part of the practitioners' workshop will consist of interesting talks and presentations by well-known speakers in the safe AI and computer vision domain. Furthermore, a call for papers will be organised, where publications in the relevant topic area for Althena can be submitted. The paper process will be peer-reviewed and double-blind. Accepted publications will be published in the conference proceedings and presented in the form of orals and posters on the workshop day. To round out the Althena practitioners' workshop experience, a panel discussion with selected experts will be envisioned to address pressing issues facing the Althena project.

The Althena consortium partners have identified that one or more of the practitioners' workshop is anticipated to be conducted in connection with the Althena project Steering Committee and Advisory Board members. The primary objective of such workshop will be to gather valuable feedback on the accomplished work within Althena, while also seeking insights to shape the future direction of the project.

5.3. Dissemination opportunities

A non-exhaustive list of relevant, both European and international conferences, workshops and other external fora has been identified and includes the following:

- IEEE International Conference on Service Oriented Computing and Applications
- IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)
- IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV).
- European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV).
- IEEE/CVF Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW).
- IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV)
- International Simulation Conference
- ITS European and World congresses
- IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems
- IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference
- International Conference on Pattern Recognition
- Asian Conference on Computer Vision (ACCV)
- British Machine Vision Conference (BMVC)
- The Autonomous Main Events
- Driving Simulation Conference Europe
- CARNET Symposium on Urban Mobility Challenges
- Symposium on Machine Learning for Autonomous Driving
- European Conference and Symposium on Connected and Automated Driving (EUCAD)
- Transport Research Arena conference (TRA)
- Conference on Results from road Transport Research (RTR)
- European Transport Conference
- Annual POLIS Conference
- Urban Mobility Days

The list of relevant conferences and events will be available for all partners, and new, applicable to the scope of Althena project, items will be added to the list. External events and meetings will be used to present the project to a wider audience, to interact with different group of stakeholders, and to validate (if relevant) project results and outcomes.

All Althena partners are encouraged to communicate and disseminate the project and its findings via presentations, speaking slots, organisation of sessions, exhibitions, presentation of posters and papers. Partners will be required to inform the WP6 leader, FIA, about any external activities' participation, and report on performed activities.

6. Communication and dissemination tools and procedures

All communication and dissemination tools, techniques, and procedures to communicate about the project and disseminate its results are described in the following paragraphs. A branding guideline has been developed that incorporates the style and colours based on the logo prepared for the Althena project.

6.1. Visual identity and branding guidelines

The visual identity and branding guidelines will be the base for all communication output material. This way, a cohesive branding will be used when communicating about the Althena project. All the following materials are shared and made available to all partners in the project.

6.1.1. Logo

The following are the logos of the project. It comes in a vertical and horizontal format. The logos are also available different colours, as shown below, to match light and dark coloured backgrounds.

6.1.2. Colours

The colour palette of the project's branding are the following three variants of blue.

The main colour is a dark blue (with the following colour reference codes: CMYK 100-92-42-47, RGB 22-30-67, #161E43).

The two secondary colours are two lighter blues. The brighter blue or cyan blue has the following colour reference codes: CMYK 100-92-42-47, RGB 3-241-255, #03F1FF. The last blue or majorelle blue has the following colour reference codes: CMYK 83-58-0-0, RGB 3-109-255, #036DFF.

	DARK BLUE CMYK 100-92-42-47 RGB 22-30-67 #161E43
	CYAN CMYK 100-92-42-47 RGB 3-241-255 #03F1FF
	MAJORELLE BLUE CMYK 83-58-0-0 RGB 3-109-255 #036DFF

6.1.3. Fonts

The main fonts for project outputs are Muli in Light, Regular, and Semi-bold, and Franklin Gothic in Medium. The Muli font will be used for all body text while the Franklin Gothic font will be used for Headings.

<p>Muli</p> <hr/> <p>Is the typo of the Althena logo. This is the typeface to be used for body text.</p>	<p>Aa light</p> <p>Aa regular</p> <p>Aa semibold</p>
<p>Franklin Gothic Medium</p> <hr/> <p>It will be used for Headings</p>	<p>Aa regular</p>

6.1.4. Templates (presentation, deliverable)

Document templates for reports and presentations in the form of a Word document and PowerPoint files have been shared with all partners to use. Partners will use these templates when communicating about the Althena project and disseminating Althena work and results. Screenshots of the documents are shared below.

Figure 4 Aithena PowerPoint presentation template

Figure 5 Althena deliverable, report Word template

6.2. Website

The Althena project website uses the domain www.aithena.eu and will be the public facing area where all public information about the project will be shared.

Other domains have also been purchased and will be redirected to www.aithena.eu to gather all interested parties in the project to one website. The purpose of this is also to avoid similar domains being used that may have no link to the project.

The other domains purchased are www.aithena-project.eu, www.horizonproject-aithena.eu and www.project-aithena.eu.

The main domain, as well as the other domains, will be maintained for the duration of the Althena project and until 3 years after the end of the project. It will enable us to publish publicly available reports, deliverables, presentations, publications, or other results to the project website. Costs for this purpose will be secured in the FIA budget (WP6 Leader).

6.2.1. Purpose

The purpose of the website is to have a place where all public information about the Althena project can be stored, shared, and promoted. The website is a communication channel for project's visibility and database for all relevant information about the project's progress, the partners involved, and the aim of the project.

6.2.1.1. Structure

The draft structure of the website includes a landing page or the home page, five sub-pages including an About page, a Partners page, a News & Events page, a Library page, and a Contact page. As part of the user campaign in *Task 6.3 End user dissemination*, dedicated pages in the main menu will be developed, providing detailed information on the 4 use cases implemented in the Althena project.

A screenshot of the homepage with the top menu is available below.

Figure 6 Screenshot of Althena website (homepage)

The *Home page* will include a short introduction of the Althena project, a video about the Althena project, a news section, and a short boiler plate about the Althena project and a box with contact information and icons to the project's social media platforms. On the bottom of the home page a newsletter registration link will be provided.

The *About page* will include a longer text about the Althena project, including goals and objectives of the project

The *Partners page* will have all the logos of the consortium partners.

The *News & Events page* will have all the latest information, such as blogs, articles and events related to the Althena project.

The *Library page* will be an area for downloads of items such as public deliverables and reports, scientific and technical publications, communication materials or campaign materials.

The *Contact page* will include details on how to contact the coordination teams responsible for the Althena project. Althena funding information will be provided here as well.

The *Use Cases page* will include information about the 4 uses cases developed in the project.

6.3. Social media channels

Two social media accounts are created for the Althena project. These will be on X (Twitter) and LinkedIn. The purpose of these accounts is to communicate about the project to the public, promote and disseminate the Althena project results and outputs to reach organisations and stakeholders who are interested in AI and CCAM technologies.

The social media accounts will be updated on a regular basis depending on the input from the projects and all partners in the project. There would be at least one post per week on X (Twitter) and one post per week on LinkedIn. The frequency of publishing considered content on Althena social media accounts can be re-evaluated upon the level of activity relevant to the project during specific periods.

Both social media channels have been already established and appropriate content to what has been done or planned in Althena project was already published on channels.

6.3.1. LinkedIn page

The LinkedIn account³ handle is @Althena.

Partners will need to follow the account and can use the account as a platform to share updates about the project's progress or events where the project is mentioned. The LinkedIn account will be managed by the FIA, Work Package 6 leader, and content will be provided by all partners.

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/althena-eu-project/>

Figure 7 Screenshot of Althena LinkedIn page

6.3.2. X (Twitter) account

The X (Twitter) account⁴ handle is @_Althena_.

Althena consortium partners will need to follow the account and can use the account as a platform to share updates about the project's progress or events where the project is mentioned. The X (Twitter) account will be managed by the FIA, Work Package 6 leader, and content will be provided by all partners.

⁴ <https://twitter.com/Althena>

Figure 8 Screenshot of Althena X (Twitter) account

6.4. Newsletters

The newsletter for the Althena project has been established using a dedicated tool and a registration form will be integrated into the public website. The newsletter will have low frequency for the first 12 months of the project and will be sent on regular basis (estimated 3 times a year) as from M13 of the project implementation. The newsletter will be sent out when there is important information to share about the project. This may include events, new publications, and other relevant information about the development of the project.

The newsletter will be distributed via the website's system and will follow all general data protection rules. Newsletters will not be sent out without prior and agreed consent of the recipients receiving the newsletter. Althena newsletters will be prepared and sent by FIA, and the content of each newsletter will be discussed and agreed in WP6 monthly meetings with all

consortium partners. The Mailchimp (GDPR compliant) platform⁵ will be used for Althena newsletter.

In addition, each newsletter will be shared on Althena’s LinkedIn and X (Twitter) channels to reach a wider audience interested in Althena’s project developments and results. The Mailchimp platform allows for further distribution of the subscriber version of the newsletter using a public version of each newsletter. Analysis of post statistics from both channels will be made and made available in the *D6.5 Report on dissemination and standardisation activities* [M36].

6.5. Communication materials (printed and digital)

6.5.1. Flyer, leaflet, brochure

The Althena project coordinator, VICOMTECH, prepared the leaflet, flyer, and/or brochure design for the project. Partners will be encouraged to print these materials when needed (physical events, internal and external communication, and dissemination activities etc.).

Digital versions are also available to reduce the likelihood of printed material being wasted. It will also allow the content to be easily adapted and updated. The materials highlight the objectives of the project, the consortium, and other relevant content for which the materials have been prepared.

Figure 9 Althena Flyer

⁵ <https://mailchimp.com/>

6.5.2. Roll-up/banner

The Athena roll-up/banner has been prepared, and printed for the purpose of visibility at events, conferences, or other physical occasions where the project is present. There is a digital version of the roll-up and all partners are encouraged to print (if needed) and adapt the content for their purpose.

The roll-up follows the Athena guidelines, and it includes the project title, logo (and other design), project objectives, consortium (logo of all partners), the website and social media channels.

AI-based CCAM: Trustworthy, Explainable, and Accountable

Project description

The AITHENA project proposes the definition of a common and harmonized methodology for AI-based CCAM solutions (perception, situational awareness, decision-making and traffic management) development and testing focusing on the **trustworthy AI** pillars (accuracy, explainability, accountability, privacy, ethics) to serve the diverse end user types: vehicle drivers, function developers, and certification/legal bodies. AITHENA will work and advance on three AI aspects: **DATA**, **AI MODELS** development and **TESTING and Validation** approaches.

Harmonized Methodology

Design Development Deployment/Testing

DATA

- Explainable, privacy preserving and traceable data management tools
- Development Framework ("DevOps") like to ensure data and model lifecycle tracking and management
- Digital Twin for data generation

AI ALGORITHMS

- AI models - research and development of explainable AI models (hybrid, physically informed, multi-modal)
- Development of human-centric AI solutions strengthening user acceptance, explainability and trustworthiness

TESTING & VALIDATION

- AI testing and validation procedures - methodology to include AI based functions and systems
- Trusted AI Key Performance Indicators for CCAM components

UC-1 Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM

UC-2 AI extended Situational Awareness / Understanding

UC-3 Trustworthy and Human understandable Decision-making

UC-4 AI based Traffic management

Project partners

Valeo, RUPPRECHT CONSULT, RWTH AACHEN UNIVERSITY, BORISPOLE UNIVERSITÄT WUPPERTAL, Infineon, TU/e, TNO, MAP, SIEMENS, virtual vehicle, TTTechAuto, Continental, FTA, vicomtech, Applus IDIADA, SIEMENS, RU

www.aithena.eu

www.linkedin.com/company/aithena-eu-project/

@_Aithena_

Funded by the European Union

Figure 10 Athena roll up / banner

6.5.3. Poster

A generic poster about the Althena project will be prepared and can be used and printed by project partners primarily when attending conferences, congresses, and other relevant external events where the project is presented.

6.5.4. Videos

An introductory video⁶ about the Althena project has been already developed by VICOMTECH, the coordinator. This video has been shared on Althena social media channels and shorter versions are also available (more suitable for content on social media), and Althena partners can use the video in their presentations about the project. The video will be made publicly available on the project website.

An additional video will be created in the later stage of the project (M36), with the project results and achievements. Both videos will be targeted at the public and media. Additional videos might be created based on the needs of the project.

6.5.5. Press releases and articles

Press releases and articles about the Althena project will be prepared by partners involved in specific conferences, events, or activities. These will then be proofread and edited by FIA, Work Package 6 leader and shared with VICOMTECH for approval before publishing on the website (especially for press releases).

6.5.6. Information campaign (user awareness campaign)

An information campaign will be led and carried out by WP6 leader, FIA, with support from all remaining partners in Work Package 6. Support can come in the form of shared inputs for messages of the campaign, and results that can be easily understood by target audiences.

The campaign (part of *T6.3 End user dissemination*) aims to educate users about the use cases developed in the project and to promote the advantages XAI in CCAM can bring to the users. To do so, an information campaign will be developed to raise awareness on the Althena Project in general and the different use cases that is being developed in the project. Regarding the general overview of the Althena Project, several messages about the project and key facts and figures will be highlighted in the form of still visuals and social media messages.

However, the focus of the campaign will be on the use cases being developed in the Althena Project. These include:

- Use Case 1 – Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM
- Use Case 2 – AI extended Situational Awareness/Understanding
- Use Case 3 – Trustworthy and Human understandable decision-making
- Use Case 4 - AI-based Traffic management

For each use case, the FIA will develop a set of messages and visuals suitable for a general audience to raise awareness on the impact of AI in CCAM. These messages will be drafted in coordination and consultation with work package leaders working on the different use cases to ensure coherence and the latest information being shared in the campaign. These messages will be shared

⁶ <https://aithena.eu/>

primarily on social media channels. All partners in Work Package 6 will support the dissemination of the messages on their digital platforms too. The messages can be shared by other partners in the project as well.

The visuals for each use case will come in the form of short videos and still images. The short videos will be derived from the project video that has already been developed. The still image visuals per use case will focus on the highlights of each use case such as the reasoning behind why this use case is valuable or relevant, and the preliminary or target results that is being developed. These visuals will be shared and discussed with work package leaders for review before publication.

The FIA will also prepare a social media calendar that lists out the messages and dates of publication on the different social media channels available from the Althena project including Twitter/X and LinkedIn. The social media calendar will be shared with all partners in the project to gather wider support, reach and visibility for the project's work and developments. Partners will be invited to follow this social media calendar, should their organisation allow it. If not, partners are highly encouraged to react or share the posts that will be disseminated on the Althena platforms.

The details and the content of the information campaign will be defined by WP6 leader with 4 Use Cases Leaders and contributing partners. In the initial stage of the campaign implementation, news articles, and Althena newsletters will be featuring details of Althena Use Cases, UCs leaders, partners involved and UCs development status. In addition, digital flyers/leaflets per Use Case will be developed, demonstrating the Althena methodology in 4 critical Use Cases and promoting the benefits that XAI (Explainable AI) in CCAM can bring to the users.

The campaign will be launched on M18 and will run until M35. Results of the online campaign (including social media and website statistics) will be announced in WP6 final report: *D6.5 Report on dissemination and standardisation activities [M36]*.

6.6. EU disclaimer and emblem, and SERI disclaimer

Beneficiaries of the EU funding must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and provide funding statement in all communication and dissemination materials (both printed and digital versions). Therefore, all Althena activities related to communication and dissemination (presentations, papers, website, social media channels, publications etc.) will acknowledge the EU funding and fulfil the requirements⁷ by including the funding disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

⁷ [Communicating your project — Acknowledgement of EU funding - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eip/eip-manual/eip-manual_en)

and the EU emblem:

Additionally, as IRU (Switzerland based partner) is financed fully by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI)⁸, all communication and dissemination materials (including deliverables) will include the following disclaimer:

“This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI).”

and the visual:

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

All necessary requirements will be communicated to the Althena consortium partners and guidelines will be provided to ensure that the acknowledgement of the EU and Swiss funding is always followed.

7. Clustering with other projects, networking, and international initiatives

7.1. Collaboration opportunities

The Althena consortium partners will seek to collaborate and cluster with other relevant existing projects to create synergies and joint activities. Althena will participate in events and workshops initiated by the European Commission and CINEA and will promote joint webinars with other projects to present results and lessons learned.

First steps toward the definition of the potential collaboration with the European flagship project Hi-Drive⁹ have been established.

⁸ [Swiss transitional measures for the Horizon package \(2021–2027\) \(admin.ch\)](#)

⁹ [Hi-Drive Deployment of Higher Automation](#)

IRU has initiated discussions between the Althena and AWARD¹⁰ project consortium to transfer the lessons learned by the latter as the AWARD project has demonstrated four use cases of automated vehicles in logistics and will end in June 2024. Actions to link the two projects could include a workshop where the AWARD partners present the evaluation results and challenges encountered during the testing phase, and a presentation of the Althena project at the AWARD final event (scheduled for 13 June 2024).

FIA and VICOM have identified opportunities to exchange and collaborate with the FAME¹¹ project on topics such Common Evaluation Methodology (CEM) and CEM Taxonomy for CCAM (in relation to work on Use Cases) and Data sharing best practices.

Two other projects have been identified for potential collaboration or exchange of lessons learned (in the case of closed projects): CONDUCTOR¹² and ArchitectECA2023¹³.

Althena consortium partners are encouraged to identify further opportunities for collaboration with relevant EU-funded projects, and European and international initiatives.

8. Monitoring and recording of project activities

8.1. Dissemination and communication channels and KPIs

The table shows the Key Performance Indicators for the communication and dissemination channels that have been identified by the Althena consortium partners and grouped accordingly:

- Althena project website, social media channels, newsletter, videos,
- Participation of Althena consortium partners in events (face-to-face and online formats),
- Althena collaboration and relevant European and international projects and initiatives,
- Althena scientific and technical publications.

Online channels (website and social media)			
Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Material downloads	< 50	50 – 150	> 150
Relevant contacts made through online channel	< 10	10 - 20	> 20
Number of blog entries	< 4	5 - 10	> 10

¹⁰ [AWARD H2020 - Scaling autonomous logistics \(award-h2020.eu\)](https://award-h2020.eu)

¹¹ [FAME - Connected Automated Driving](https://fame-project.eu)

¹² [CONDUCTOR \(conductor-project.eu\)](https://conductor-project.eu)

¹³ [ArchitectECA2030 \(architect-eca2030.eu\)](https://architect-eca2030.eu)

Newsletter contact list	< 100	100 - 300	> 300
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Conferences, workshops, and webinars

Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of conferences	< 6	6 - 10	> 10
Number of people reached per event	< 50	50 - 150	> 150

Clustering with other projects, networking, and international initiatives

Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of projects and/or activities	< 3	4 - 7	> 8

Scientific and technical publications

Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of articles accepted by peer-reviewed journals	< 2	3 - 5	> 6

Project videos

Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of viewers of videos	< 100	100 - 1000	> 1000

Table 7 Dissemination and communication channels and KPIs

8.2. Communication and dissemination register

An excel table which serves as a register for all communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities which will be performed during the implementation of the Althena project, has been prepared and made available to all partners on Althena SharePoint/Teams.

The register will play twofold role, on one side as a repository of all activities relevant to communication, and dissemination of the project. On the other side it will be used as a supporting document for the final reporting period and be part of the report/deliverable *D6.5 Report on dissemination and standardisation activities* (M36).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
	Nº	Month of project	Date	1)booth, stand (exhibition), 2)participation in/speaking at a conference, congress, 3)organisation, participation in a special session, 4)participation in a workshop, 5)participation in other events, 6)participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s), initiatives, 7)other activity	Type of event	Title of event	Location	Title of presentation, panel discussion, session etc.	Responsible partner	Involved partners	Type of audience	No of participants	Description
1													
2	1	5	08/03/2023	5	IRU members meeting update	CTP meeting (Passenger transport meeting)	Brussels	Research & Innovation update	IRU		IRU passenger transport members	30	
3	2	6	16-19/04/2023	2	International event	Automotive Week 2023. Smart. Sustainable. Safe.	Helmond, the Netherlands	Key note speech by Margriet van Schijndel - de Nooij		TUE			

Figure 11 Screenshot of the Athena register file.

9. Scientific and technical publications

9.1. Identified scientific and technical publications

Athena will make all scientific and technical publications stemming from the conducted research available through gold or green open access. We will select the most appropriate journal for each specific paper.

Examples of relevant peer-reviewed journals that have been identified by the Athena consortium include:

- IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
- Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory
- IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
- IEEE Open Journal of ITS
- IEEE Transactions on ITS
- IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles
- IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology.

Moreover, scientific, and industry-oriented conferences will be excellent platforms to disseminate our findings and start direct conversations with the varied types of audience relevant to the Athena project.

9.2. Open Science

Athena project will contribute to the European vision “Open innovation, open science, open to the world”¹⁴ which represents an innovative approach to the scientific process based on cooperative work and new ways of diffusing knowledge by using digital technologies and new collaborative tools.

Athena partners will be encouraged to support publications of scientific papers and generated datasets to open access journals and repositories such as zenodo.org¹⁵ and the European Open

¹⁴ [Open innovation, open science, open to the world | Shaping Europe’s digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

¹⁵ [Zenodo - Research. Shared.](#)

Science Cloud¹⁶, which provide open access to scientific publications and the research outcomes following the FAIR guiding principles (making results *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable* – see *Data Management Plan*). As for the publication strategies that aims to disseminate and exploit the scientific achievements of the project:

- On publication of foreground: The Parties are encouraged to publish the material related to the public deliverables of the project. All partners will be responsible for publishing project results, in local and international press, and in peer-reviewed scientific journals and at conferences.
- On the access to knowledge: The principal interface for knowledge access, both internally and externally, will primarily be achieved through the Althena website which will contain the public deliverables as well as the list of scientific publications with the external link. The partner will be requested to create a profile on a repository (e.g., Zenodo) to pursue the dissemination of Gold Open Access publications.
- Publication guidelines: The consortium, following the GA regulations and IPR, is encouraged to publish on ISI journals the project results with Gold and Green open access modalities. The project's board of partners will define when data should not be published open access, and the WP6 Leader will monitor publications. Open access publications will be available in "Gold" open access, and budgets have been set aside accordingly.
- Althena Results: External collaboration through the Github (or similar) repositories.
- Datasets to be shared following Open Data and Data Lake principles (work to be done in *Task 6.4 OpenData plan and OpenTool plan and sharing*, results will be published in *D6.2 Report on data sharing and integration with European data lakes, OpenData and OpenTool [M36]*).

¹⁶ [EO SC Portal \(eosc-portal.eu\)](https://eosc-portal.eu)

10. List of acronyms and terms

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Autonomous Intelligent Systems
ADS	Automated Driving System
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automotive Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
DX.X	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
H2020	Horizon 2020
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MX.X	Milestone
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturers
SERI	Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation
TX.X	Task
RIA	Research and Innovation Actions
RDW	The Netherlands Vehicle Authority
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence